

ISic1436

I.Sicily inscription 1436

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, Antiquarium di Megara

Hyblaia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330081

1. Καλιοψ [— —] ²⁷Καλιοψ[ίον](?) = Καλλιοψίου (Guarducci)²⁷
2. εἶμι.
- 3.

Edition: PHI330148

1. Καλιόψ [ιός] ²⁶Καλλιόψιός²⁶
2. εἶμι.
- 3.

Edition: PHI331813

1. Καλιοψ [ίον] ²⁶Καλλιοψίου²⁶ ²⁷Καλιόψ[ιός] = Καλλιόψιος²⁷
- 2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644979

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PHI 330081

PHI 330148

PHI 331813

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